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Studies on Thermal Properties of Cadmium tungstate catalyst

P. K. SINHAMAHAPATRA* and S.K. BHATTACHARYYA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005.

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CADMIUM tungstate is reported to have effective catalytic activity for a number of industrial reactions at the temperature range 250°-425°¹⁻⁵. Literature on the physicochemical properties of this tungstate is extremely meagre. In the present note the results on the method of preparation, differential thermal analysis (DTA), thermogravimetry (TG), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and magnetic susceptibility of fresh cadmium tungstate and its various thermal transition products have been presented.

Experimental

Preparation and chemical analysis of the catalyst :

100 ml. of cadmium sulphate octahydrate (12.8 g. per 100 ml. of water) saturated at room temperature was added slowly (5 ml. at a time) to a saturated solution of sodium tungstate dihydrate (16.5 g./100 ml. water) followed by digestion for 45 min. at 70°-80°. The substance was allowed to settle, filtered off, washed with hot water and ultimately dried in an air-oven at 110° for 24 hr. The catalyst was pure white. W⁶ in solution was analysed as WO₃ by precipitation with HCl and HNO₃ (50 : 50) in presence of quinine and calcination at 700°-800°. Cd²⁺ in solution was analysed as cadmium molybdate by precipitation with ammonium molybdate solution in feebly acetic acid medium at 90° and calcination at 120°. The amount of water was determined by estimating hydrogen using Coleman Carbon-Hydrogen Analyzer.

Procedure :

The experimental set up and the procedure followed by the authors were the same as described by Bhattacharyya et al. ^{6,7} previously. The X-ray diffraction patterns of samples obtained by heating the fresh tungstate at 250°, 440° and 900° (for 2 hours in

each case) were taken. Magnetic susceptibilities of these samples were measured by Faraday method at 24° using Hg [Co (NCS)₄] as calibrant.

Results and Discussion

The chemical composition of cadmium tungstate is established as CdWO₄ · 1.1/2 H₂O (Cd-29.05%, W-47.78%, H₂O-6.75%).

DTA and TG curves are shown in Fig. 1. The DTA curve shows a sharp endothermic peak at 195° followed by an endothermic change at 315° and a baseline drift within 440°-850°. The TG curve registers a total weight loss amounting to 7.62% within 110°-850°. The weight loss up to 250° is 4.1% which corresponds to removal of one molecule of water from one molecule of CdWO₄ · 1.1/2H₂O. The rest water, however, is lost within 260°-860°.

Fig. 1. DTA and TG of Cadmium tungstate

X-ray analysis of the catalyst samples heated at 110° and 250° exhibits the same XRD patterns with the relevant lines at $d = 3.787, 3.050$ (characteristic), 2.547, 1.910, 1.806, 1.762, 1.546 Å. The XRD patterns of the 440° preheated sample appear to be more distinct than observed in the preceding cases. The characteristic d -values calculated are 3.819, 3.050, 2.533, 1.806, 1.756, 1.546, 1.523, 1.457, 1.398 Å. Thus, the structure of the fresh sample is crystalline and the removal of the adsorbed water molecules from the large tungstate molecule does not cause any change in the crystal structure of the system. The characteristic d -values, e.g., 3.81, 3.050, 2.533 Å, etc. compare excellently to those reported for standard patterns of CdWO₄ (A.S.T.M. Card 1-0488).

The original catalyst sample is diamagnetic and this property remains unaffected upto melting.

*Present address : Catalyst Section, Indian Institute of Petroleum, P. O., I.I.P., Mohkampur, Dehra Dun-248 005, U.P. (India).

